

Straw, lime, and manganese dioxide amendments for iron-toxic rice soils

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A nutritional disorder of lowland rice associated with excess water-soluble Fe often occurs on strongly acid soils. It has been identified in the Philippines, Vietnam, Thailand, Malaysia, India, Sri Lanka, Liberia, Senegal, Colombia, and China. Lime and MnO_2 alleviate the disorder.

In the greenhouse, we evaluated the effect of straw (0 and 0.25%), $CaCO_3$ (0 and 0.25%), and MnO_2 (0 and 0.005%), in a $2 \times 2 \times 2$ factorial, randomized complete block design in 4 replications on the growth and yield of IR26 in an iron-toxic acid soil. NPK was added to soil collected from the top 20 cm of a Sulfaquept from Malinao, Albay, Philippines. The soil had pH 3.4, 0.64% organic C, 0.049% total N, 2.4% active Fe, 1.3 mmol/kg exchangeable K, and 4.4 mg/kg available P (Olsen). Four 20-d-old IR26 seedlings were transplanted in each pot 2 wk after submergence. The soil solution was analyzed fortnightly.

Although 4 wk after transplanting (WAT), Fe concentrations in the soil

1. Influence of straw, $CaCO_3$, and MnO_2 on the kinetics of water-soluble Fe^{2+} in a submerged iron-toxic soil, IRRI.

2. Grain and straw yields as affected by different additive treatments, IRRI.

3. Fe content of shoots at 4 WAT and straw at harvest as affected by different additive treatments, IRRI.

solution differed mainly in the lime factor (Fig. 1), Fe toxicity symptoms were severe in untreated soil, moderately severe in straw-treated soil, mild in MnO_2 -treated soil, and virtually absent in all lime treatments. Eight wk after transplanting, plants on straw-treated soil began to recover, which may be associa-

ted with declining Fe concentration in the soil solution.

Lime alone or combined with MnO_2 produced the highest straw and grain yields (Fig. 2). The benefits of lime were associated with lower concentrations of Fe in the soil solution and in rice shoots (4 WAT) and mature straw (Fig. 3). Straw and MnO_2 alone or combined gave moderate yield increases which were associated with a lower Fe content of the shoots (4 WAT) than in the untreated plants.

As an inexpensive amendment for iron-toxic soils, straw merits further study. We need to ascertain

1. if smaller amounts of N, P, and $CaCO_3$ are sufficient, when combined with the straw, to prevent N and P deficiency and Fe toxicity in early stages of rice growth;
2. how long the residual effects of straw, lime, and MnO_2 incorporation will last; and
3. what is the optimum amount of straw and timing of transplanting. □

Effect of soil moisture and seeding depth on seedling emergence of two rices

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We evaluated the effect of soil moisture content and seeding depth on seedling emergence of Safri 17 and IR36. Seeds were planted in a loam soil in the laboratory at 1, 2, 3, and 5 cm deep and water was applied 1, 2, or 3 cm deep.

The figure gives percent seedling emergence as influenced by depth of water application based on isolines of percent emergence. When IR36 was planted 5 cm deep, seedling emergence was low. Percent emergence for Safri 17 was similar at seeding depths of 1 and 5 cm.

Soil moisture level corresponding to soil water potential between -0.5 to -2.0 bars was most favorable for seedling